
Edo State Federal Inland Revenue Services Staff's Views on Digital Taxation and Sustainable Economic Development

Sadiq Oshoke Akhor¹ & Isaac Azenabor²

¹ Department of Accounting
Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria
akhor.sadiq@aauekpoma.edu.ng; +2348025912721

² Department of Political Sciences
Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria
isaacazenabor@aauekpoma.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874131>

Abstract

The researchers investigated the effect of digital taxation on sustainable economic development. A survey research design was adopted while simple random sampling technique was employed to administer structured questionnaire to one-hundred (100) staff of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) in Edo State, Nigeria. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and simple linear regression correlation were used to analyse the data. The empirical findings showed that digital taxation has a significant effect on sustainable development. The researchers recommended that the government of Nigeria should consider the digitalisation of the tax system and administration for contributing immensely to sustainable development of the economy.

Keywords: Benefit Received Theory of Taxation, Digital Taxation, Sustainable Economic Development and Taxation

Introduction

Digital taxation is a new phenomenon for the digitalisation of the tax system through innovative means for enhancing sustainable economic development in Nigeria. A digital taxation economy focused mainly on non-resident company (NRC) for the effective usage of technology in the administration, collection and payment of tax by the relevant stakeholders and tax payers. An economy may be seen as the way a resource of a given society is distributed among the people living in the society (Grimsley, 2018, cited in Yakubu & Kadiri, 2019; Aslam & Shah, 2020). However, a country may experience an economic growth without the economy been developed, depending on the level of development of a country and the technological advancement of such a country the two words can be viewed differently.

Economic development is the problem of underdeveloped countries and economic growth to those of developed countries. The raising of income levels is generally called economic development. The identification and development of a gap followed by the will and effort to seize existing opportunities are essential to the entrepreneurial process

through the process of digital communication (Rajamohan & Sathish, 2020). Lyla (2021) argued that the challenges of digital presence in African markets are the emergence of bilateral treaties signed with countries commanding digitalisation of e-services. Digital companies providing e-services are Amazon, Uber, Alibaba, MoneyGram and Western Union to users in decentralised financial services without a physical presence in the country. Digital presence in African leads to mismatch between tax rules and digitalisation of the economy. However, digital taxation creates niche for strengthening the tax administration, fighting against tax evasion and other tax loopholes in the tax system for effective generation of tax revenue for the government. The Finance Act of 2020 amended the relevant tax laws in accordance with macroeconomics policy reforms of the Federal Government for imposing tax on digital services in the country.

Before the introduction of e-tax administration in Nigeria, the tax system has been impaired by untold irregularities, inconsistencies, difficulties in filing and collection of tax revenue (Oladele, Aribaba, Adediran, & Babatunde, 2020). Meanwhile, developing economies embraced digital taxation to thrive for sustainable economic development and growth via e-registration, e-payment, e-filing, e-receipt, e-stamp duty and e-tax compliance cost without visiting tax offices. Opeyemi, Stephen, Samuel, Olokoyo & Damilola (2022) maintained that adoption of digitalisation in the Nigerian economy is a major boost to sustainable economic development through which the government have the potential of securing financial inflows through the digital services and prevent capital flights. However, unfriendly tax policies and mal-administration may create an avenue for capital flight from Nigeria to other emerging and developed countries with more friendly tax policies. Before now, consulting firms and other internet services firm evade tax in Nigeria by repatriated funds to the domestic country where incomes, profits and revenues either generated or earned. Extant literature underpinning the nexus between digital taxation and sustainable economic development has been limited in scope using Nigerian context. Hence, the research gap created in knowledge is to investigate the effect of digital taxation on sustainable economic development.

Concept of Sustainable Economic Development

Sustainable economic development is the measures adopted by governments in the collection of revenue to meet expenses of governance through the delivery of adequate and desirable infrastructures (Oladele *et al* 2020). Sustainable economic development is premised on economic growth which is the increase in the amount of the goods and services produced by an economy over time which is measured as the percent rate of increase in real gross domestic product or real GDP. However, a country may experience an economic growth without the economic been developed, depending on the level of development of a country and the technological advancement of such a country the two words can be viewed differently. Economic development is the problems of underdeveloped countries and economic growth to those of developed countries. The raising of income levels is generally called economic development. But these views do not specify the underlying forces which raise the income levels in the two types of economies.

The problems of under developed countries are concerned with the development of unusual resources, even though their uses are well known, while those of advanced countries are related to growth, most of their resources being already known and developed to a considerable extent. Development and growth have nothing to do with the type of economy. Sustainable economic development hinge on the total monetary of all finished goods and services that are produced in a particular country (Fernando & Boyle, 2021 cited in Agbo & George, 2022). The goal of the Nigerian tax system is to contribute to the well-being of all Nigerians directly through improved policy formulation for sustainable growth, and development indirectly through appropriate utilisation of tax revenue generated for the benefit of the people. Therefore, an efficient and robust tax system is the cornerstone to attaining the Nigeria's ambition of becoming one of the most rapidly developing economies of the world (Adedeji & Oboh, 2012).

Overview of Taxation

Taxation is a vital instrument for fiscal stability and economic development (Ibrahim, Tahir, Zannah & Bature, 2022). Taxes are imposed by many sub-national entities. Taxes consist of direct tax or indirect tax and may be paid in money or as its labour equivalent. In essence, tax is seen as pecuniary burden put upon individuals or property to support the government in its oversight activities of a nation and exacted by legislative authority. Apart from oil revenue driving the Nigerian economy, other sources of government revenue is mainly borrowing, fees, fines, and or taxes (Areo, Gershon & Osabuohien, 2020). The amount of tax revenue generated by a government for its expenditure programmes depends among other things, upon the willingness of the taxpayer to comply with the tax laws of the country. The tax revenue system in Nigeria has to be strengthened to ensure more income redistribution and reduction of poverty in Nigeria (Anyadub & Otulugbu, 2019).

Digital Taxation

The introduction information technology has created room for digital taxation (DT) for information dissemination between taxpayers and tax authorities. Digital infrastructures like modems, computers and mobile phones as well as phone applications, computer programmes and networks of integrated wireless service providers has gain prominence in tax administration (Opeyemi *et al* 2022). The inclusion of digital services in the administration and collection of taxes between the general public and government, this mechanism helps to reduce the incidence of tax avoidance and tax evasion practices committed by taxpayers. Tax avoidance can be seen as a trigger in tax management activities that is used for tax planning and have an arrival point for tax evasion. It is simply a strategy deployed by managers, a set of processes, practices, resources and choices whose objective is to maximise income after all company's liabilities owed to the state and other stakeholders (Boussiadi & Hamed, 2015).

Digital Taxation is a form of e-taxation platform explored in the collection and administration of tax revenue (Oladele *et al* 2020). It implies a holistic process of using digital based- technologies in the administration of tax from the Federal level to the local

level. The new mechanism adopted by tax authorities in the tax system for the efficient collection of tax from taxpayers is digital taxation. The digital services for the registration, generating personal identification number (PIN), filing of returns and application for a compliance certificate is adopted for effective administration of tax. However, the e-service tax system such as e-registration, e-payment, e-filing, e-receipt, e-stamp duty and e-tax compliance cost was introduced in the administration of taxes in Nigeria (Akpabi & Igbekoyi, 2019). In the assertion of Lucas-Mas & Junquera-Varela (2021), Digital taxation is a wholesome process of digital economy for effective administration of taxes. Digital taxation is a technological driven platform built on digital content, digital automation, digital communication, digital distribution and digital payment through other electronic devices.

Benefits of Digital Taxation to the Nigerian Economy

According to Anushiem (2023), the following are the benefits of digital taxation in Nigeria and this is the citadel of economic development:

- Taxation of digital economy will create more revenue for the government.
- Taxation of non-resident taxpayers under the digital economy will widen the Nigerian tax net.
- Movement of the economy from an oil-based to a tax-based economy.
- Reduces the incidence of borrowing by the Nigerian government.
- Reduces the level of debt servicing by the government.
- Promotion of e-tax administration.

Reviews of Empirical Studies

Sweet's (2020) research work on US claimed impasse on digital services tax talk; from the study, it was revealed that digital taxation would negatively impact on sustainable development. This indicates that digital taxation significantly reduces trade and investment, innovation, economic growth and development. Etim, Jeremiah & Dan (2020) studied the effect of the digital economy on tax compliance in Nigeria. Primary data were collected through the distribution of questionnaire while descriptive and inferential statistics in the analysis of data. The empirical evidence showed that digital economy had a significant negative effect on tax compliance. Oladele *et al* (2020) examined the effect of e-tax administration on tax compliance and tax revenue in Nigeria. Data were collected from the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) for seven (7) years period before and after the adoption of e-tax administration in 2013 and analysed using descriptive statistics and pairwise t-test. The result showed that a positive relationship exist between e-tax system and tax revenue growth. Akpabi & Igbekoyi (2019) sampled fast-food restaurants in Lagos to examine the effect of e-taxation on tax compliance. Copies of questionnaire were distributed to SMEs owners within Lagos. The results showed that the level of awareness has a significant positive effect on tax compliance at 1% level, perceived ease of use had a significant positive effect on tax compliance at 5% level and tax compliance cost had insignificant negative effect on tax compliance.

Chijioke, Leonard, Bossco & Henry (2018) conducted an empirical study on pre

and post-analysis of the impact of e-taxation on Nigeria's revenue and economic growth. Quarterly data were collected from Federal Inland Revenue Service, Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical and Economic Reports for the period of 2013 to 2016 and analysed, using regression technique. The result showed e-taxation implementation had insignificant negative impact on tax revenue.

Theoretical Framework

The benefit received theory of taxation was propounded by Wicksell (1896) cited in Ibrahim *et al* 2022) was explored to buttressed the study. The theory postulates that tax payers who pay taxes to the government should receive through the provision of infrastructural facilities and other social amenities as a way of reciprocating and encouraging them in the payment of tax. However, foreign companies enjoying digital presence in Nigeria and compliance with the relevant tax laws in the payment of taxes as enshrined in the Nigeria Finance Act 2021. These companies benefit from uninterrupted broadband and other infrastructural facilities in the area of digital elements like digital content, digital automation, digital communication, digital distribution and digital payment been classified as digital economy activities.

Methodology

A survey research design was adopted in this study. The population comprises staff of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) in Edo State, Nigeria. The population size defined the scope of the study within which the research findings were applicable. The research instrument used was self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was constructed on a 5 point Likert scale: 1, strongly disagree, 2, disagree, 3, undecided, 4, agree and 5, strongly agree on the variables of interest (digital taxation and sustainable economic development). The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha statistics. From the result, sustainable economic development has a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.707 while digital taxation has a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.701. This signifies that the research instrument used in this study exhibits a high degree of reliability, making it well-suited for gathering the essential information from the respondents. The simple random sampling technique was used to sample one-hundred (100) respondents and data were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and simple linear regression technique via SPSS version 23.0. A simple linear regression model was specified to test the hypothesis of the study. The regression model with error term was specified as:

$$SEC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DT + e_t,$$

Where;

SED= Sustainable economic development.

DT=Digital taxation.

e_t , = Error term.

Presentation and Analysis of Results

The presentation and analysis of result started with the correlation analysis which was presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis

		SED	DT
SED	Pearson Correlation	1	.445**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	90	90
DT	Pearson Correlation	.445**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	90	90

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2024/SPSS

Table 1 above showed the correlation analysis result indicating that digital taxation has a positive and moderate correlation with relationship with sustainable economic development (DT =0.445). This, therefore, means that the presence of digital taxation might lead to improve in sustainable economic development with a significant value of 0.000.

Regression Analysis

Simple linear regression technique is employed to test the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. The summary of result of the linear regression analysis is presented in the table 2 below.

Table 2: Summary of the Regression Result

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.445 ^a	.198	.188	.44559	2.249

a. Predictors: (Constant), DT

b. Dependent Variable: SED

It is observed from table 2 above that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable has the value of 0.198. This implies that 20% of the variation in sustainable economic development was explained by digital taxation. This was supported by the adjusted R² of 0.188.

In order to check for the presence of autocorrelation in the model, Durbin-Watson statistics is employed. Durbin-Watson statistics value of 2.249 in table 2 showed that the variables in the model are not auto-correlated and that the model is reliable for predictions. The effect of digital taxation on sustainable economic development is presented in table 3 below.

Table 3: Significant Effect of Digital Taxation on Sustainable Economic Development

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	1.898	.497		3.821	.000
DT	.637	.137	.445	4.655	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SED

Source: Field Survey, 2024/SPSS

It was observed from table 3 that digital taxation has a positive coefficient value of 0.637 and t-statistics value of 4.655 with a significant value of 0.000. This implies that digital taxation has a significant positive effect on sustainable economic development (SED =0.000) at 1% level of significance. The positive coefficient value of digital taxation means that there was 99% confidence level that the presence of digital taxation would significantly improve sustainable economic development with sig-value < 0.05.

Discussion of Findings

The regression result showed that digital taxation has a significant positive effect on sustainable economic development. The finding is consistent with the findings of Oladele *et al* (2020) that a positive relationship exists between e-tax system and tax revenue growth. The findings of Sweet (2020) also supported the result that digital taxation has a significant negative impact on sustainable development. The finding is contrary to the findings of Bossco & Henry (2018) that e-taxation implementation had insignificant negative impact on tax revenue.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study was conducted to investigate the effect of digital taxation on sustainable economic development. Digital taxation is a new phenomenon for the digitalisation of the tax system through innovative means for enhancing sustainable economic development in Nigeria. The inclusion of digital services in the administration and collection of taxes between the general public and government, this mechanism helps to reduce the incidence of tax avoidance and tax evasion practices committed by taxpayers. The descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and simple linear regression were used to analyse the data. It was concluded from the empirical findings that digital taxation has a significant effect on sustainable development. It is, therefore, recommended that the government of Nigeria should consider the digitalisation of the tax system and administration for contributing immensely to sustainable development of the economy.

References

- Adedeji, T.O. & Oboh, C.S. (2012). An empirical analysis of tax leakages and economic growth in Nigeria (Unpublished Research Work).
- Agbo,E.I. & George, E. U. (2022). Effect of online system of taxation on Nigerian economic growth. *GOUNI Journal of Faculty of Management and Social Sciences*, 10(1), 143-159.
- Akpubi, M. D. & Igbekoyi, O. E. (2019). Electronic taxation and tax compliance among some selected fast-food restaurants in Lagos state, Nigeria (taxpayers perspective), *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 7(7), 52-80.
- Anushiem, C.M. (2023). Appraisal of the prospects for taxation of digital economy in Nigeria. *UNIZIK, Law Journal*, 19 (2), 33-40.
- Anyaduba, J.O. & Otulugbu, P.O. (2019). Taxation and income inequality in Nigeria. *Accounting and Finance Research*, 8(3), 118-135.

Edo State Federal Inland Revenue Services Staff's Views on Digital Taxation and Sustainable...

- Areo, O.S., Gershon, O. & Osabuohien, E. (2020). Improved public services and tax compliance of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria: A generalised ordered logistic regression. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 10(7), 833-860.
- Boussaidi, A. & Hamed-Sidhom, M. (2020). Board's characteristics, ownership's nature and corporate tax aggressiveness: New evidence from the Tunisian context. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 5(1), 1-12.
- Chijioke N.O., Leonard, I.A., Bossco E.O. & Henry, C.A. (2018). Impact of e-taxation on Nigeria's revenue and economic growth: A pre-post analysis. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(2), 19-26.
- Etim, Jeremiah. & Dan (2020). Tax compliance and digitalisation of Nigerian Economy: The empirical review excise duty (Amendment) (No.2) Act, 2018.
- Ibrahim, M., Tahir, F.A., Zannah, M.M. & Bature, R. (2022). Taxation of digital economy: A paradigm shift towards improved tax revenue in Nigeria. 4th ICAN-Malaysia International Conference on Accounting and Finance (ICAF-IMDS 2022), 4-12.
- Lucas-Mas, C.Ó. & Junquera-Varela, R.F. (2021). Tax proposal for taxing the digital economy. *Markets*, 4-6.
- Lyla, L. (2021). The evolving thunder: The challenges around imposing the digital tax in developing African countries. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3901962
- Oladele, R., Aribaba, F.O., Adediran, R.A. & Babatunde, A.D. (2020). e-tax administration and tax compliance among corporate taxpayers in Nigeria. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 4(3), 93-101.
- Opeyemi, A., Stephen, O., Samuel, F., Olokoyo, F. & Damilola, E. (2022). Tax reforms, digitalisation and government revenue in Nigeria. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 12(9), 800-815.
- Rajamohan, S. & Sathish, A. (2020). Entrepreneurial Opportunities for the Sustainable Development of Madurai Tourism. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(5), 1597-1604.
- Sweet, P. (2020). US claims impasse on digital services tax talk. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367254470_Taxation_of_Digital_Economy_A_Paradigm_Shift_Towards_Improved_Tax_Revenue_in_Nigeria
- Yakubu, A. & Kadiri, U. (2019). Empirical review of globalisation and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research (IJPAMR)*, 5 (1), 58-70.